

THE IMPACT OF BUILDING INFORMATION MODELING (BIM) TECHNOLOGY ON THE QUALITY AND ACCURACY OF DESIGN IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

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Abstract

This article examines the impact of Building Information Modeling (BIM) technology on the design processes in the construction industry. It explores the role of BIM in improving the quality and accuracy of design solutions, minimizing errors, and enhancing collaboration among project participants. The use of a unified digital model for work coordination, change management, and ensuring data transparency is studied. Examples of successful BIM implementation in complex projects are provided, demonstrating its efficiency in reducing timelines, lowering costs, enhancing team communication, and increasing design accuracy.

Keywords: Building Information Modeling (BIM), design accuracy, design quality, construction project management, digital model, clash detection, automation, visualization.

Introduction

Modern construction industry faces several challenges regarding design accuracy improvement, resources management optimization, and cost reduction over the entire built facilities lifecycle. One of the forefront technologies to reduce those issues is Building Information Modeling (BIM). This technology collects information related to a given project, its construction activities, and operational elements under a single digital umbrella by allowing greater transparency and better control. In the recent years, BIM has been in the mainstream of design and construction management processes in most of the developed countries.

The benefits of BIM extend far beyond basic design: the technology helps reduce errors, increase calculation accuracy, and accelerates decision-making. Despite its clear advantages, the adoption of BIM comes with several challenges, including the retraining of specialists, changes to organizational processes, and high implementation costs. In this context, studying the

impact of BIM on key aspects of design, such as quality and accuracy, becomes particularly important. The purpose of this study is to analyze the impact of BIM on the quality and accuracy of design in the construction industry and to identify key factors that contribute to the effective implementation of this technology.

Main part. BIM capabilities in enhancing design quality and accuracy

Modern construction design demands increasingly higher standards of quality and accuracy. Errors in the design phase can lead to significant financial losses, project delays, and safety risks. BIM technology offers tools and approaches that significantly improve the quality of design solutions and achieve a high level of accuracy [1]. Research shows that BIM results in a reduction of rework costs by 49 % and schedule duration by 57 %, respectively [2]. These advantages make it a preferred tool among construction industry specialists. According to a 2023 report [3], 70% of construction professionals adopted BIM in their projects (fig. 1).

Fig. 1. BIM adoption among worldwide construction professionals without 2022 data, %

One of the key advantages of BIM is **the creation of a unified digital model** that incorporates the geometric, physical, and functional characteristics of all elements of the designed object. This eliminates the data fragmentation often encountered with traditional design methods.

The integration of BIM allows architects, engineers, and builders to work within a single model, preventing inconsistencies in design solutions. As an example, HVAC systems (heating, ventilation, and air conditioning) are automatically checked for clashes with structural elements [4]. These tools enable precise calculations of materials, loads, and other parameters,

reducing the likelihood of errors caused by human factors. A notable example is the use of BIM in designing high-rise buildings, where calculation accuracy and team coordination are critically important. The digital model allows for the early detection and resolution of conflict points, which are often only identified during the construction phase in traditional design approaches [5].

BIM provides effective tools for the **automatic quality checking of design solutions**. One of its most important features is clash detection. This technology identifies conflicts between different building systems during the design phase.

Clash detection allows for the automatic identification of physical intersections between elements, such as pipelines and load-bearing structures [6]. This feature is particularly relevant for complex infrastructure projects where multiple engineering systems interact. It also enables the simulation of various usage scenarios for the building, helping to detect potential issues before construction begins. It allows engineers to analyze how structural loads will change under different operating conditions, ensuring the integrity and efficiency of the design.

Advanced visualization and analytics capabilities provided by BIM **improve design quality**. This will allow designers, clients, and beneficiaries to more clearly analyze the project and its details in three-dimensional models.

Photo-realistic 3D modeling enabled by BIM helps project teams and clients understand what the building will look and feel like long before the first shovel hits the ground. In these BIM digital models lies an embedded level of information useful in analyses such as energy efficiency, acoustic performance, and lighting intensity, among many other parameters. This facilitates the optimization of design solutions to meet specific client requirements. Designing a residential complex with BIM allows for the early modeling of the building's energy efficiency, calculating the optimal thickness of insulation, window configurations, and building orientation relative to the cardinal directions.

Data transparency in BIM systems is achieved through the automatic recording of all changes in the model. Any action, whether adding a new element or modifying the parameters of an existing one, is logged in the model's record. This simplifies project control and makes the process more understandable for clients, who can track the progress of work in real time. Such transparency fosters trust among project participants and prevents misunderstandings during data transfer in the construction phase.

The application of BIM technology has found **widespread use in various construction projects**. In the development of large-scale infrastructure buildings, such as airports, precision is of paramount importance. The BIM technology facilitates the elimination of thousands of conflicts between systems, such as ventilation, water supply, and electrical installations [7]. It is also actively employed in the restoration of architectural heritage. The scanning of structures and the creation of digital models ensure precision in planning restoration work, reducing the risk of damage to significant historical elements [8].

As demonstrated by Epicon's practice, the BIM tool can be extensively utilized in the design of water

supply and water discharge facilities, as well as industrial cooling systems [9]. In the case of water supply and discharge, BIM enables precise modeling of pipeline networks, reservoirs, and pumping stations, ensuring optimal routing of utilities and preventing clashes with other engineering systems. For industrial cooling systems, BIM supports the design and analysis of complex heat exchange loops, equipment placement, and pipeline routing. This significantly reduces the time required for design approvals and minimizes the likelihood of errors. These capabilities make BIM an indispensable tool in the development of engineering projects with a high degree of technological complexity.

The technology behind BIM provides designers with powerful tools to increase the quality and accuracy of design. Data integration, process automation, and improved visualization make BIM an indispensable tool for complex construction projects. The use of this technology leads to the creation of higher-quality structures, minimizes errors, and reduces the time required for their resolution, ultimately saving time and resources. BIM does not merely improve the design process but fundamentally transforms the approach to managing construction projects.

Improving communication and project development efficiency

Communication is required at each construction site, particularly when one discipline and participant interact with another, for example, architects, engineers, contractors, and clients. Most traditional modes of interaction involve inconsistencies in data, raising many problems associated with delays and increased costs. Therefore, BIM Technology enhances collaboration among teams involved and the effectiveness of project development by embedding collaborative workflows and tools.

One of the primary advantages of BIM is the ability for all project participants to collaborate within a unified digital environment, known as the Common Data Environment (CDE). This space serves as a central platform for storing, updating, and sharing data, providing real-time access to all necessary information:

- **Unified data source:** all participants work with the most up-to-date model, eliminating errors caused by outdated documentation. For instance, changes made by an architect are automatically reflected for engineers and contractors.

- **Distributed access:** cloud-based solutions allow specialists to make updates and discuss the project regardless of their geographical location, which is especially relevant for international or remote teams. This feature greatly accelerates decision-making processes and makes collaboration between teams more transparent and efficient.

Improved communication within project teams and enhanced interaction with clients, investors, and other stakeholders are facilitated by BIM. Using 3D visualizations and interactive models, project solutions can be presented in a clear and understandable manner. Three-dimensional models help clients better understand the concept and proposed solutions, reducing the likelihood of misunderstandings. Thanks to project visualizations, stakeholders can suggest changes or clarifications in real time, reducing the number of revisions at later stages. Using virtual reality (VR) based on BIM models allows clients to "walk through" the building before its construction, enabling more informed and

precise decisions. At the same time, researchers note that the use of BIM technology, despite its numerous advantages in improving communication among project participants, can be accompanied by certain risks [10]. In particular, disputes related to the manage-

ment, verification, or ownership of digital models become more likely in the context of multi-party collaboration. The need to coordinate actions among architects, engineers, contractors, and clients also requires clear communication to prevent misunderstandings and organizational conflicts (table 1).

Table 1

An overview of the advantages and disadvantages of BIM in many sectors of building projects

Category	Aspect	Advantages	Disadvantages
Legal and contractual	Communication	Improved communication between stakeholders	None
	Dispute resolution	Facilitated dispute resolution	Potential disputes over model management, verification, or ownership
Risk management	Mitigation and contingency planning	Enhanced mitigation and contingency planning	None
	Claims and litigation	Reduced likelihood of claims and litigation	Higher liability for contractors using BIM
Dispute resolution	Early identification and resolution of disputes	Facilitated early identification and resolution of disputes	None
	Mutually agreeable outcome	Improved chances of reaching a mutually agreeable outcome	

In industrial project design, BIM helps synchronize work between design teams and contractors, reducing the risk of discrepancies between project documentation and actual construction work. In projects involving specialists from different countries, such as infrastructure development, BIM eliminates language barriers and standardizes information exchange.

Modern tools provided by BIM significantly improve communication among project participants and enhance the efficiency of project execution. By creating a unified information environment, enabling interactive visualizations, automating change management, and increasing process transparency, BIM becomes an indispensable tool for complex construction projects. Implementing this technology reduces approval times, lowers organizational risks, and ensures more cohesive collaboration across all teams.

Conclusion

The BIM technology demonstrates a significant impact on the quality and accuracy of design, transforming the construction industry and establishing new standards for project management. A unified digital model, process automation, data integration, and enhanced visualization enable the reduction of errors, optimization of time and resource expenditure, and increased transparency in collaboration among participants. These advantages make BIM an indispensable tool for executing complex projects, securing higher levels of efficiency and sustainability. The adoption and advancement of BIM open vast opportunities for further digitalization of the construction industry and the enhancement of its processes.

References

1. Yarov Y. Modern architectural approaches to building design: integrating eco-friendly solutions and

advanced technologies // New science: from idea to result. 2024. № 11. P. 139-147.

2. Abdelbary M, Edkins A, Dorra EM. Reducing CRR in fast-track projects through BIM. *Journal of information technology in construction*. 2020 Jan 1;25.

3. DIGITAL 2023 CONSTRUCTION REPORT. NBS IN ASSOCIATION WITH Glenigan. 2023. 51 p.

4. Gourabpasi AH, Nik-Bakht M. BIM-based automated fault detection and diagnostics of HVAC systems in commercial buildings. *Journal of Building Engineering*. 2024 Jun 15;87:109022.

5. Manzoor B, Othman I, Kang JM, Geem ZW. Influence of building information modeling (Bim) implementation in high-rise buildings towards sustainability. *Applied Sciences*. 2021 Aug 19;11(16):7626.

6. Luo S, Yao J, Wang S, Wang Y, Lu G. A sustainable BIM-based multidisciplinary framework for underground pipeline clash detection and analysis. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 2022 Nov 10;374:133900.

7. Keskin B, Salman B, Ozorhon B. Airport project delivery within BIM-centric construction technology ecosystems. *Engineering, construction and architectural management*. 2020 May 15;28(2):530-48.

8. Charlton J, Kelly K, Greenwood D, Moreton L. The complexities of managing historic buildings with BIM. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*. 2021 Mar 15;28(2):570-83.

9. Projects / Epicon // <https://epicon.biz/en/projects> (date of application: 08.12.2024).

10. Alotaibi BS, Waqar A, Radu D, Khan AM, Dodo Y, Althoey F, Almujiab H. Building information modeling (BIM) adoption for enhanced legal and contractual management in construction projects. *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*. 2024 Jul 1;15(7):102822.